

Disaster and climate education (DCE)

Reflections from the 2025 European symposium of the Disaster and Climate Education Network

José Pastrana Huguet

Introduction

Climate change is currently one of the most pressing concerns for our societies. Various studies have affirmed a broad consensus among the academic community that climate change is a reality and that its causes are anthropogenic (Cook et al., 2013, 2016; Doran et al., 2009; Oreskes, 2004, 2018; Lynas et al., 2021). In this regard, the latest Assessment Report published by the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC), known as the Sixth Assessment Report or AR6, exposes the numerous adverse effects that an increase in average temperature above 1.5 degrees Celsius would have on the planet. The report warns that, without an immediate reduction in emissions across all productive sectors, it will be impossible to limit global warming (IPCC, 2023). As the IPCC noted in its previous Climate Report of 2018, curbing warming requires unprecedented changes that will affect almost all aspects of human life, since exceeding the 1.5 degrees Celsius limit could have devastating and irreversible consequences, endangering the planet's biodiversity and causing an increase in intensity and frequency of extreme weather events (IPCC, 2018; IPCC, 2023).

The effects of human-caused global warming are already occurring, are irreversible on the timescale of people living today, and are expected to worsen in the coming decades. We are already seeing the effects, including the loss of sea ice, melting of glaciers and ice sheets, rising sea levels, and more intense heatwaves and storms (NASA, 2024). Climate models indicate that temperature changes will not be uniform; polar and land regions are expected to experience

the most significant increases. Precipitation will vary across the planet's regions, with wetter and drier areas. Nearly 900 million people live in coastal areas vulnerable to sea level rise, especially in densely populated countries and Pacific islands. Sea level rise is already forcing the relocation of inhabitants in these areas (IPCC, 2023; NASA, 2024).

Europe is the fastest-warming continent and faces significant climate risks that affect energy, food, ecosystems, infrastructure, water resources, the economy, and health (REF). Extreme events, such as heatwaves, floods, and droughts, will become more common and intense, with regions particularly vulnerable in the south and low-lying coastal areas. The European Environment Agency (EEA) warns that Europe is not prepared to face these risks, which could become catastrophic without urgent and coordinated action. Specific adaptation measures and fostering cooperation between countries and regions are essential (EEA, 2024). In this context, to achieve resilient societies in the face of disasters, education and skills development is crucial to increase the population's awareness of disaster risks, and to encourage action and adaptation in values, attitudes and behaviours as already set out in the Hyogo Framework for Action (UNDRR, 2005) and in the current Sendai Framework (UNDRR, 2015), which emphasizes the importance of education for disaster risk reduction, highlighting the need to integrate this knowledge into educational systems (Olcina, Morote, 2025).

The Disaster and Climate Education Network (DCEN) is an international research and cooperation network dedicated to linking education, climate change, and disaster risk reduction. Founded by researchers from Germany, Spain, and England, it aims to facilitate exchange on national approaches, identify challenges, and promote innovation in Disaster and Climate Education (DCE) within and between a diverse group of communities and stakeholders.

The network seeks to:

- bring together knowledge, experiences, and research outcomes,
- bridge the gap between theory and practice,
- develop comparative and interdisciplinary perspectives, and
- initiate collaborative projects and educational strategies that strengthen societal resilience.
- Something about impact and action?

DCEN views education (both formal and informal and intergenerationally) as a key driver for disaster preparedness and climate adaptation. Through interdisciplinary and participatory collaboration among researchers, educators, communities, public institutions, and civil society, the network works to design and implement learning processes for prevention, adaptation, and sustainable action.

Academic literature in DCE reveals a broad body of international research providing valuable conceptual, formal, and practical insights. From a **conceptual and theoretical perspective**, Kitagawa (2021) identifies three ways of conceptualizing disaster education, highlighting its interdisciplinary. Preston's edited volume (2012) further deepens this reflection by showing, through examples from the United Kingdom and the United States, how DRR communication and education have historically prioritized the protection of certain social groups over others. Similarly, Shiwaku et al. (2016) analyze the evolution of DRR in Japan, emphasizing governance structures, curriculum development, and teacher training as key to fostering resilience across educational systems. Regarding the **school sector**, several studies focus on integrating DCE into formal curricula and teacher education. Selby and Kagawa (2012) conducted a comparative study of disaster risk reduction in school curricula across thirty countries, identifying major gaps and promising practices. Kitagawa (2023) explored how topics related to climate change, sustainability, and disaster risk reduction are addressed in secondary teacher education programs in England and Japan. Yildiz et al. (2023) examined the relationship between disaster experience, education, and socioeconomic context in shaping children's perceived risk and preparedness in Nepal and Turkey. In the **non-formal and community context**, Shaw et al. (2011) argue that disaster education must go beyond the school environment to include families and communities, thereby strengthening collective preparedness and social resilience. Overall, however, it is evident that many contributions to adult education are interdisciplinary and that adult education science has so far paid little attention to the topic (Lacher & Rohs, 2023; Lacher 2025). **Comparative studies**, such as Pastrana (2024), highlight the relationship between preventive culture and disaster risk management in Spain and Japan, positioning education as the essential link between knowledge, action, and community engagement.

This report presents, from a comparative perspective, how DCE and climate change effects are being addressed in three European countries: Germany,

Spain, and England. The initiative originated from a group of researchers from these countries¹, who founded the DCEN and held an international symposium at the University of Kaiserslautern-Landau. Participants discussed the status of DCE in the three participating countries and the resulting gaps in our understandings and need for action, ranging from informal learning to formal education in schools and universities.

2. Objectives, methods, and development of symposium

The symposium's objectives were aimed at both critical analysis of the current situation and international knowledge exchange on DCE. First, the symposium focused on the current situation regarding DCE in Germany, Spain, and England, identifying both progress and persistent challenges. Second, it sought to delve deeper into local practices in these countries to identify gaps in knowledge to develop an innovative project. The preparation and development of the symposium were organized as detailed in Figure 1.

Six virtual meetings were undertaken to prepare for the symposium. It was decided to invite two guest speakers from each country, who have experiences of implementing DCE in the country. In total, the symposium participants were 12 – six guests and six DCEN members. It was then decided to create a summary of describing the legal context and key practices of DCE in Germany, Spain, and England, so that each participant would have a basic understanding of the country contexts. To deepen collective understanding and enrich academic exchange, 'a library' was created in which all 12 participants share two of their

¹ List of core members:

Kaori Kitagawa, University College London (UCL), UK

Hans Svennevig, University College London (UCL), UK

Matthias Rohs, University of Kaiserslautern-Landau (RPTU), Germany

Sophie Lacher, University of Kaiserslautern-Landau (RPTU), Germany

Elisa Isabel Gavari Starkie, National University of Distance Education, Spain (UNED), Spain

José Pastrana Huguet, National University of Distance Education (UNED), Spain

relevant publications. This enabled participants to learn about the approaches and results of previous research of other participants and identify common interests.

The symposium was organized over three days in Kaiserslautern (Germany). On the first day, after an initial networking session to understand the researchers' concerns, a debate was held, followed by a brainstorming session on the field of DCE. The debate and brainstorming focused on three key questions:

- What do we understand by DCE?
- What is missing in DCE research/practice?
- Where are the links to climate risk, and how can we integrate them into our research perspectives?

The second day was divided into two working sessions. It began with a communication from each of the experts invited, followed by a discussion among all participants. The aim was to gain perspectives on the challenges and problems in education based on their research and practice, enrich collective understanding, and gain insight from other perspectives.

Communications by experts from the UK:

- DCE initiatives implemented focused on the challenges of climate change, by Dr. Sara-Jayne Williams, University of the West of England.
- Reflections on DCE with children, by Dr. Ayse Yildiz, University of Leicester.

Communications by experts from Spain:

- DCE in Valencia: Challenges and gaps before and after the 2024 floods, by Dr. Carmen Grau Vila, Institute for Sustainable Community and Risk Management of the Waseda University, Senshu University, and Universitat Oberta de Catalunya (UOC).
- Knowledge, skills, and attitudes for disaster risk reduction and other 21st-century challenges, by Dr. María Inmaculada Navarro González, National University of Distance Education (UNED).

Communications by experts from Germany:

- The German Civil Protection System and the Role of Education, by Kathrin Stolzenburg, Federal Office for Civil Protection and Disaster Relief, Bonn.
- Challenges and Problems in DCE: Learning from Emergency Response Teams: A Study of Transformative Experiences and Transformative Learning, by Dr. Saskia Eschenbacher, Akkon University of Berlin.

The second session featured a participatory dynamic structured around three working groups. At each group, a moderator facilitated the discussion and ensured that all voices were heard. Participants rotated between groups every 15 minutes, allowing each participant to contribute their perspective and benefit from the insights of other colleagues.

Each group focused on a key question, designed to encourage reflection and generate ideas for future research development. The questions were:

- What research, questions, methods, or theories do we need to explore?
- What questions can be included in a competency framework?
- What expertise will we draw into DCE Research?

At the end of the roundtable rotation, a briefing session was held, where they shared their most relevant findings. This collective exercise allowed for the identification of points of convergence, opportunities for collaboration, and the laying of the groundwork for a joint research and education agenda on disasters and climate change.

The third day focused on analyzing the conclusions drawn from the previous sessions, thereby bridging the gap between theoretical reflection and practical action. The main findings and points of convergence identified in the roundtables were reviewed to define a shared vision and outline next steps for strengthening education and research on disasters and climate change. The guiding principles that will guide the Network and future lines of action were considered.

3. Country contexts

The following section presents the results of the symposium, derived from an examination of the legal frameworks in the United Kingdom, Spain, and Germany, as well as the contributions of the participants and the discussions that arose from the key questions addressed in the focus groups.

3.1. Legal context and key practices of DCE

3.1.1. Legal context and key practices of DCE in Germany

3.1.1.1. The system of civil protection in Germany

Germany is organized as a federal state in which constitutional law divides responsibilities between the Federal Government and the federal states ('Länder'). According to Article 73 I,1 of the Basic Law (Federal Ministry of Justice, 2025) and the Civil Protection and Disaster Relief Act (ZSKG, BBK, 2020), the Federal Government is responsible for civil defense. The institutions entrusted with these tasks include the Federal Ministry of the Interior (BMI), the Federal Office of Civil Protection and Disaster Relief (BBK), the Federal Agency for Technical Relief (THW), the Federal Armed Forces, and the Federal Police. In peacetime, the primary responsibility for responding to natural disasters, such as storms or floods, lies with the federal states, which delegate many tasks to their subordinate municipalities. It is in these municipalities that operational implementation is carried out, for example, by fire brigades or relief organizations. In the case of disasters of national importance, the Federal Government supports the Länder. Together, the Federal Government, the Länder, the municipalities, and relief organizations such as the German Red Cross (DRK), the Federal Agency for Technical Relief (THW), and the (voluntary) fire brigades form the integrated system of all protection and assistance services known as "civil protection".

3.1.1.2. DCE in Germany

Germany offers almost no DCE or preparedness initiatives for the general public—neither through formal curricular measures nor through national campaigns in formal education (Chadderton, 2015). For a long period of peacetime after the Cold War, Germany was considered a relatively safe country because it was less affected by natural disasters (Chadderton, 2015). For a long time, the government paid little attention to the risks of disasters and largely excluded the public from disaster preparedness and awareness campaigns

(Kitagawa et al., 2016). Highly trained volunteer units – especially the THW and volunteer fire brigades – are the main providers of civil protection and disaster relief (Chadderton, 2015). However, flood events such as the Elbe flood (2002 & 2013) and the Ahrstal flood (2021), the coronavirus pandemic, and the changed risk situation in Europe have led to increased public interest in disaster preparedness (Geicht, 2022). However, both older studies and current surveys indicate that the German population tends to be insufficiently prepared for disasters, both in terms of food preparedness and essential skills (Kitagawa et al., 2016; Geicht, 2022; Rohs, Lacher & Großmann 2025). The existing information campaigns by the federal government (BBK), federal states, and local authorities also appear to have a rather low level of awareness (Geicht, 2022; Rohs, Lacher & Großmann 2024). Since 2020, initiatives such as the annual nationwide Warning Day have tested sirens, warning apps, and mobile-phone alert systems in real-world conditions to both verify their effectiveness and increase public awareness of disaster risks (BBK, n.d.). In addition, aid organizations offer some courses, such as 'First Aid with a Self-Protection Content', as well as courses offered by some individual adult education centers (Volkshochschulen'). The extent to which civil defense should also be taught in schools is currently under discussion. Baden-Württemberg is the first federal state to make disaster control an integral part of the curriculum. This includes first aid, among other things. The range of self-help online learning content provided by the state and aid organizations is constantly expanding. Additionally, there are guidebooks, various magazines, and numerous online resources that offer information on civil protection (Rohs & Lacher 2025).

3.1.1.3. DCE in Germany

Germany's DCE framework is guided by the "National Action Plan on Education for Sustainable Development" (National Platform on Education for Sustainable Development, 2017), which aims to integrate the UN 2030 Agenda SDGs, interdisciplinary modules, and risk assessment skills across all educational levels. At school level, the Standing Conference of the Ministers of Education and Cultural Affairs of the Länder (KMK) and the Federal Ministry of Education and Research (BMBF) have recommended that the topics of climate change and resilience be included in the geography and science curricula at lower and upper secondary level and that DCE be integrated as a cross-cutting topic in schools (KMK, 2024). Schools decide on their own responsibility and authority how to implement DCE in school and extra-curricular learning, as well as in school life

(National Platform on Education for Sustainable Development, 2017). In adult education, the umbrella organization of the adult education centres (DVV) recommends that 'Volkshochschulen' embed sustainable development in their mission statements and program offerings based on the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), and provides informational materials on the National Action Plan along with templates to support local implementation (National Platform on Education for Sustainable Development, 2017). Further offers, such as the online "BNEhoch3" (BMBF, n.d.) program for multipliers, provide twelve modular units on climate change, the energy transition, and adaptation strategies, culminating in certification.

3.1.2. Legal context and key practices of DCE in England

3.1.2.1. The system of Civil Protection in England

The 2004 Civil Contingencies Act established a framework for emergency planning and response, defining Category 1 and 2 responders. The former are at the core of the response to most emergencies, such as emergency services and local authorities; the latter are 'cooperating bodies' such as transport and utility companies. Category 1 and 2 organizations jointly form Local Resilience Forums to help coordinate between responders. As a Category 1 organization, the Environment Agency leads flood risk management for the sea, main rivers, and reservoirs, and issues flood warnings to high-risk areas. The Climate Change Act 2008 is the UK's climate change mitigation framework (UK Government, 2019). The act also requires the government to assess the risks of climate change through a National Adaptation Programme renewed every 5 years (UK Government, 2024b). The 2010 Flood and Water Management Act designates some local councils as Lead Local Flood Authorities (LLFAs), which are responsible for managing flood risks within their areas. Flood risk management within communities is predominantly organized voluntarily by community members (UK Government, 2024a). The National Flood Forum, established in 2002, plays a vital role in supporting and representing communities at risk of flooding. This charity helps establish flood action groups (FAGs) and provides practical support to communities (National Flood Forum, 2020). FAGs are a key component of flood risk management across the UK.

3.1.2.2. DCE in England

In formal schooling, the Department for Education (DfE) produces the National Curriculum setting out the areas of study schools must provide to pupils. The National Curriculum covers both primary and secondary schools, and all local authority-maintained state schools must deliver it by law. The National Curriculum was introduced in the Education Reform Act 1988 in tandem with the new framework of Key Stages as year groups. Geography is the main subject area that engages with the topics related to natural hazards and risks (Kitagawa, 2023). Following the government's introduction of the sustainability and climate change strategy (DfE, 2023), Climate Change and Sustainability Education (CCSE) is a fast-growing field of study in the UK. The strategy positions the curriculum as a key driver of climate literacy by strengthening climate education across subjects, improving access to high-quality resources, and aligning teaching with the green skills needed for a climate-impacted future. The strategy also emphasises practical and real-world learning and embeds sustainability into everyday practice through integrated planning and clear sustainability leadership.

The 1974 Health and Safety at Work Act requires employers, including schools, to take reasonable steps to protect employees, pupils, and visitors' health and safety. It applies to both on- and off-premises activities, such as school visits. Schools must consider emergency procedures for severe weather and community disasters (UK Government, 2022). The DfE provides guidance, like 'Emergency planning and response for education, childcare, and children's social care settings' to help educational providers plan for emergencies, minimize disruption, and safeguard children's welfare across various settings (Department for Education, 2024).

The Equality Act 2010 is also relevant to DCE. The act protects people from discrimination in society, stipulating who is protected from discrimination, the types of discrimination under the law, and what action can be taken if you feel you have been unfairly discriminated against (UK Government, 2015).

3.3. Legal context and key practices of DCE in Spain

3.1.3.1. The system of Civil Protection in Spain

The normative basis for Spanish civil protection is Law 17/2015, which establishes the National Civil Protection System. Additionally, Spain has articulated a system that includes the Basic Civil Protection Standard complemented by the General State Emergency Plan for Civil Protection (PLEGEM). The National School of Civil Protection (ENPC) aims to meet the training needs of the National Civil Protection System's human resources and collaborate with the civil protection training centers of other Public Administrations, promoting the recognition of official professional training degrees and professional certification. Training in civil protection and emergencies in Spain is a shared competence among the Education, Employment, and Civil Protection organizations, dependent on the three levels of Public Administration: General State Administration, Regional Administration, and Local Administration. These administrations are responsible for issuing certificates and providing continuous civil protection training.

3.1.3.2. DCE in Spain

In formal education, the Professional Training system has included the Technician in Civil Protection Emergencies and the Senior Technician in Emergency Coordination and Civil Protection since 2013, regulated by Royal Decrees 906/2013 and 907/2013. The current education law in Spain from 2020 (LOMLOE) does not refer to DCE. The law only mentions environmental risks but does not link them to disaster risk. In Spain, a model more focused on sustainability and responsibility in the fight against climate change has been chosen (Gavari et al., 2021). Although education for preventing natural and anthropogenic risks is contemplated transversally in subjects such as Geography, Biology, or Education for Citizenship, secondary education on disaster risk management has no specific subject or mandatory block. The Spanish Climate Change Law of 2021 dedicates a section to teaching about climate change (Title VIII, "Education, Research, and Innovation in the fight against climate change and the energy transition"). This section includes two articles: Art. 31, "Education and training in climate change," and Art. 32, "Research, development, and innovation in climate Royal Decree 524/2023 change and energy transition."

3.1.3.3. New lines of action in Civil Protection and DCE in Spain

The consequences of the Dana in Valencia have highlighted weaknesses in disaster risk education. To address these weaknesses, on November 11, 2024, the Government launched a disaster training plan, which will be mandatory for all students in Spanish schools starting in the 2025-2026 school year. According to the plan, students from Kindergarten to Secondary will learn about safety rules, prevention, risk identification, psychological support for victims, emergency alert systems, and tools to detect misinformation during these disasters.

The plan was designed jointly by the Ministry of Education and the Ministry of the Interior. Staff from emergency intervention and assistance services, along with collaborators and Civil Protection volunteers, will deliver the talks to students. Additionally, it is expected that teachers can complement this training after receiving training from the National School of Civil Protection or regional Civil Protection schools, earning permanent training points that will count towards their curriculum. The goal is to prepare the entire population, including children, to face natural disasters and other adverse weather phenomena that are becoming more frequent in Spain. The Government has established minimum content that the Autonomous Communities and schools can expand to address relevant contingencies according to the area's natural, social, or economic characteristics. These minimum contents are divided into five blocks.

1. Addresses emergency alert systems.
2. To help students and teachers identify risk situations in their environment.
3. Cover prevention and self-protection measures to mitigate the effects of floods, coastal risks, earthquakes, tsunamis, volcanic eruptions, fires, industrial accidents, chemical, nuclear, and hazardous transportation incidents.
4. Dedicated to psychological support and available resources for victims.
5. Information against misinformation in emergencies.

On December 16, 2025, the 2024 National Civil Protection Strategy was approved, which includes strategic objectives in this area and their lines of action. The strategy works on the following objectives:

- Anticipation: determining the risks in a territory according to vulnerability conditions and possible threats.

- Prevention: promoting measures and actions to avoid or mitigate the potential adverse impacts of emergency risks and threats.
- Planning: contribute to preparing all public administrations to respond to emergencies in a planned manner by establishing preparation measures in advance to act effectively.
- Response: promoting immediate response actions to emergencies related to public emergency intervention and assistance services by regulatory standards.
- Recovery: encouraging effective post-disaster recovery measures considering the principles of collaboration, cooperation, coordination, inter-territorial solidarity, subsidiarity, efficiency, participation, inclusion, and universal accessibility for people with disabilities.

3.2. Three key DCE questions

At the initial discussion at the symposium on Day 1, participants identified key questions most relevant to DCE in the three country contexts. This was described in a flipchart as follows.

Figure 2: Results reflected in the flipchart of the first session

1. What is Disaster Climate Education (DCE)?

- Convenient/ Practical
- Knowing isn't enough, practice and skills are also needed
- Dealing with unexpected
- Disaster Risk Reduction Education
- Critical thinking

2. What is missing in DCE?

3. How to integrate DCE?

- Lots to do!!

Question 1: What is Disaster Climate Education (DCE)?

DCE encompasses the knowledge, skills, and attitudes needed to understand, mitigate, and adapt to the risks associated with natural and man-made disasters, particularly those exacerbated by climate change. Its main components include:

- Risk Management: teaching people and communities to identify, assess, and reduce risks before a disaster occurs.
- Crisis Management: developing the capacity to respond effectively during and after disasters, minimizing damage and facilitating recovery.
- Disaster Management: integrating preparedness, response, and recovery strategies into daily life and through institutional planning.
- Convenience and Practicality is necessary to ensure that education is accessible and applicable, based on real-life scenarios.
- From Knowledge to Action: it is concluded that awareness alone is not enough; practical skills, regular drills, and community engagement are equally vital.
- Addressing the Unexpected: cultivating adaptability, resilience, and quick thinking in the face of unforeseen events is necessary for an effective response.
- DRR action: proactive measures must be incorporated through education to minimize impacts before they occur.
- Critical Thinking: analytical capacity must be fostered not only among managers but also among communities to assess situations, solve problems, and make informed decisions under pressure.

Question 2: What is Missing in DCE?

Despite its importance, DCE often faces shortcomings that limit its effectiveness. These include:

- Practice and preparation: opportunities for hands-on learning through simulations and preparation exercises are sometimes lacking.
- Long-term planning: sustainable strategies that go beyond short-term responses are needed, which require commitment and continuous adaptation.
- Expert organizations: greater collaboration between specialized agencies and experts is needed to provide up-to-date, evidence-based content and training.

- Consensus and educational strategy: the need for unified approaches and well-defined frameworks across institutions, communities, and government agencies is identified.
- Bottom-up approaches: One of the shortcomings observed is that communities are not always considered. Therefore, it is necessary to involve local communities in the creation and implementation of educational initiatives, ensuring relevance and cultural sensitivity.
- Virtual Reality (VR) and Visual Practice: technology should be leveraged to enhance immersive learning and simulate complex disaster scenarios.
- Research: While research exists in this area, there is still a need to promote empirical studies and integrate research findings to inform and update educational content.
- Educational Perspective and Longitudinal Studies: long-term evaluations are needed to measure the impact of DCE and guide continuous improvement.
- Teacher training and education: educators must be provided with the tools and knowledge necessary to deliver effective continuing education programs in DCE to students, including ongoing professional development for teachers.
- Community studies and communication: dialogue between educators, students, and communities is lacking in ensuring that messages are clearly understood and practical.
- Disaster relief and experimental research: integrate real-life case studies of disaster relief and experimental approaches to validate and refine educational techniques.
- Informal approaches and empirical research: recognize the value of both formal instruction and informal learning, supported by data-driven information.

Question 3: How to Integrate DCE?

Based on the two previous questions and in response to this question, effectively integrating DCE requires a multifaceted and holistic approach. Integrating DCE is a dynamic and collaborative effort that requires innovation, commitment, and adaptability. Much remains to be done.

3.3. Communications by experts

Day 2 started by six guest speakers' presentations. They were asked to share challenges, problems or gaps they face in their work.

3.3.1 Communications by experts from Germany

3.3.1.1 The German Civil Protection System and the role of Education

Stolzenburg's presentation focuses on the German Civil Protection System and the role of education within it.

The German civil protection system is based on a clear distribution of powers between the federal government and the federal states (Länder), ensuring an effective response in both peacetime and severe crises. The federal government, under Article 73.1 of the Basic Law (Grundgesetz), assumes primary responsibility in times of war or significant external threats. In these scenarios, it is responsible for coordinating civil protection at the national level, ensuring the defense and security of the population. For their part, the Länder, according to Articles 30 and 70, are responsible for managing civil protection in peacetime, including prevention and assistance in the event of natural disasters, industrial accidents, and other catastrophes. They also collaborate with the federal government in situations beyond their capabilities, and Article 35 regulates cooperation and mutual assistance between the different levels of government in the event of disasters, facilitating the joint use of material and human resources.

The German civil protection structure is decentralized, allowing each level of government, along with various institutions, to play a key role. The federal government designs national strategies, coordinates international humanitarian aid, and establishes general guidelines. The Federal Office for Civil Protection (BBK) coordinates civil protection activities at the federal level, developing regulations, organizing training, and managing strategic resources. States and local authorities are responsible for rescue services, fire protection, and direct technical assistance to the population, maintaining a close relationship with the BBK to ensure the consistency of their actions.

BBK was founded in May 2004 and currently has an annual budget of over €200 million and approximately 720 employees. The organization's internal structure consists of five specialized departments, in addition to a central services department. BBK's main tasks include developing and updating national

protection strategies, protecting and monitoring critical infrastructure such as hospitals, power plants, and communication networks, as well as promoting volunteerism and citizen emergency preparedness. It is also responsible for training in areas such as disaster medicine, chemical, biological, radiological, and nuclear (CBRN) threats, and temporary shelter management. BBK also trains management and operational staff, ensuring the professionalization of response teams, and provides psychosocial support to both victims and responders. It also coordinates information and resources between different agencies and levels of government and develops early warning systems for citizens in the event of imminent threats.

Civil protection education plays a strategic role in emergency preparedness and response. It promotes collective resilience and strengthens society's capacity for self-care in adverse situations. It facilitates safe and adequate decision-making in complex and changing environments, contributes to the professionalization of both volunteers and permanent staff, and increases public trust in the institutions responsible for their protection.

Civil protection training in Germany spans different levels and institutions. At the federal level, the Federal Academy for Civil Protection and Disaster Management (BABZ) and the Federal Agency for Technical Aid (THW) offer specialized programs. At the state level, there are 15 fire academies in the Länder dedicated to technical and operational training. Voluntary organizations, such as the ASB, the DLRG, the DRK, the JUH, and the MHD, provide training to their members and promote community preparedness. In addition, some universities and technical training centers offer specialized programs and courses in civil protection, risk management, and emergencies.

According to Stolzenburg, significant challenges remain. Civil protection education is not explicitly regulated in many laws, which can affect the consistency and quality of programs. The fragmentation of responsibilities between different levels of government can lead to duplication or gaps in training. Furthermore, a gap persists between general educational policies and the internal policies of civil protection organizations. Educational approaches are often based on isolated projects and lack systematic development. Therefore, it is essential to strengthen the organizational resilience of educational institutions, ensuring their capacity to adapt and innovate in the face of new challenges and threats.

3.3.1.2 Challenges and Problems in DCE: Learning from Emergency Response Teams: A Study of Transformative Experiences and Transformative Learning,

Dr. Eschenbacher's presentation, based on two previous studies (Eschenbacher, 2023; Eschenbacher & Marsick, 2024), addresses how traumatic experiences affect emergency professionals and what changes are necessary to address them successfully.

The main challenges identified are that emergency professionals are unprepared to address the emotional impact of their work. The researcher detects a lack of coping strategies among these professionals. She believes that the technical training received ignores the emotional component. Mental health training is insufficient due to a lack of understanding of the long-term effects of traumatic experiences. A high level of burnout is observed, with some leaving the profession due to a lack of institutional support. Finally, the unintended consequences of poor management of traumatic experiences are highlighted, such as loss of empathy, emotional suppression, and mental health-related stigma.

The researcher identifies systemic barriers for emergency professionals, including a toxic work culture, where stigma toward those who display emotional vulnerability persists, making it difficult for professionals to seek help. Risks to professional development, given that requesting psychological support can have negative consequences for professional development, reinforcing resistance to seeking help for trauma. Other factors include a lack of adequately trained supervisors; this lack of mental health training limits the ability to detect and address emotional exhaustion in teams during traumatic events. A lack of trauma treatment specialists is detected, which hinders access to adequate psychological and emotional treatment interventions. Finally, a resistance to change is detected in institutions, where technical aspects are prioritized, and there is little flexibility to incorporate psychoemotional care.

Regarding proposals to improve the management of traumatic experiences in emergency professionals, the researcher suggests that it is necessary to transform the management of traumatic experiences in emergency services to break the culture of silence and stigma surrounding mental health, redefining emotional vulnerability as a strength, and promoting self-care and seeking help. It is essential to balance technical training with the development of emotional

resilience through workshops, simulations, and spaces for reflection, as well as reviewing internal policies that may entail sanctions for requesting psychological support, ensuring confidentiality, and the protection of labor rights. Likewise, the creation of support networks through mentoring and discussion groups strengthens the sense of belonging. It reduces isolation by complementing technical briefings with safe spaces for expressing and processing emotions, thereby facilitating their normalization and coping. Only a comprehensive approach that values both the technique and humanity of professionals will protect their well-being in the face of these experiences.

3.3.2 Communications by experts from Spain

3.3.2.1 DCE in Valencia: Challenges and gaps before and after the 2024 floods

Dr. Grau's presentation is based on her research on flood management in Valencia, focusing on DCE and the challenges and gaps before and after floods.

The Valencian Community, located on the east coast of Spain, has historically been exposed to significant flooding. From the devastating flood of 1957 to the recent floods of 2024, the population has experienced recurring episodes that have highlighted its vulnerability to extreme weather events. Despite the passage of decades, the exposure and fragility of infrastructure, along with a lack of systematic preparedness, have continued to perpetuate the risk in the area. One of the key factors in this vulnerability has been insufficient effective risk education, as well as a lack of robust communication and early warning systems. Efforts to prepare citizens and institutions have, in many cases, fallen short of real needs, exacerbating the impact of disasters.

The floods of 2024 marked a turning point in the collective memory of Valencia. A total of 75 municipalities were severely affected, with the province of Valencia being the most severely hit. Approximately 306,000 people suffered the direct effects of the disaster, with 37,000 rescues carried out in extreme situations. The human toll was particularly tragic: 235 deaths were recorded (227 in the Valencian Community, seven in Castilla-La Mancha, and one in Andalusia), 2,600 people were injured, and 117,000 people were treated in emergency centers. In terms of material damage, more than 10,000 homes were destroyed and nearly 70,000 businesses were disrupted. Rainfall reached a historic record, with 777.8 liters m² in just 24 hours, collapsing drainage and protection systems.

Prior to the disaster, the education system and institutions faced significant deficiencies. There was a significant gap between risk management regulations and their actual implementation in schools and municipalities. Regular drills were adapted to local plans, but specific teaching materials for disaster preparedness and education were lacking. In the past 12 years, only two school trials related to risk management were conducted, an insufficient number to create a culture of prevention. Training for emergency professionals was limited, which in turn limited response and prevention capacity. Furthermore, the minimization of alerts for economic and tourism reasons hampered adequate social risk preparedness.

Following the disaster, Valencian society has mobilized in an exemplary manner. Local emergency and reconstruction committees have been created, bringing together residents, technical staff, and municipal representatives, who coordinate assistance and recovery efforts. For example, the DANA Citizen School (Escola Ciutadana) emerged as a pioneering initiative, organizing workshops, talks, and activities in neighborhoods, associations, and auditoriums, focusing on self-protection, emotional management, and resilience in the face of future events. These experiences demonstrate the capacity of citizens to organize and complement institutional responses, promoting a culture of prevention and solidarity.

Despite progress, fundamental challenges remain. Coordination between policymakers and the scientific community is still limited; reconstruction has prioritized technical and infrastructure aspects, relegating the social and educational focus. Partnerships between city councils and university researchers have enabled the review of local plans and the promotion of risk assessments, as well as training in schools and community centers. However, these efforts remain uneven and require further systematization. The gap between science and society remains, as misinformation, institutional mistrust, and a tendency to minimize risks complicate the adoption of preventive behaviors.

To move toward a more prepared society, it is necessary to reflect on key questions. How can we close the gap between existing regulations and their effective implementation at all levels? What strategies can be integrated to strengthen formal risk education in the Spanish system? How can scientific research influence public risk management policies? How can we improve communication and the link between science and policy at the local and national

levels? What specific actions can strengthen disaster memory in education and civic culture?

3.3.2.2 Knowledge, skills, and attitudes for disaster risk reduction and other 21st-century challenges

Dr. Navarro's communication, based on two previous investigations (Gavari et al., 2021; Navarro et al., 2024), highlights the fundamental importance of soft skills in the training of future teachers, situating the analysis in the European and Spanish context. These competencies are essential not only for professional performance but also for facing the social, technological, and environmental challenges that characterize the 21st century. In a world where constant transformation and uncertainty are the norm, soft skills are consolidated as essential tools for adaptation, educational leadership, and the management of complex challenges such as DRR.

Various international institutions have provided frameworks for the development of soft skills and disaster risk management. Since 1993, the World Health Organization has promoted life skills related to decision-making, empathy, and stress management, essential elements for responding to emergencies. The OECD and the European Union have promoted key competencies, including problem-solving and teamwork, both essential in daily life and in responding to critical situations. Furthermore, the Institute for the Future highlights the importance of adaptive thinking and social intelligence, skills that are especially valuable for preventing, preparing for, and responding to natural or human-made disasters.

In Spain, the importance of these competencies is reflected in educational legislation and professional qualification frameworks. The LOMLOE (Spanish Law on the Law of Education and Training) promotes the inclusion of transversal competencies, including critical thinking, personal autonomy, and active participation. The Spanish Qualifications Framework for Higher Education (MECES) also includes training in skills that foster collaboration, effective communication, and informed decision-making.

Studies in teacher training show that soft skills are valued more than actual mastery. This highlights the urgent need to strengthen the development of these competencies, including those related to disaster risk. The most significant gaps between perceived importance and actual mastery are found in pressure tolerance; intercultural relations, crucial for managing diverse teams and

communities during a crisis; adaptation to change, essential for responding to unforeseen events; decision-making, necessary for making responsible and ethical choices under pressure; oral communication, essential for conveying clear instructions; and networking, key to establishing support and collaboration networks.

Current formal education does not fully respond to the human and environmental challenges of the 21st century, including disaster risk reduction. Teachers must assume the role of agents of change, systematically integrating both soft skills and risk management principles at all educational levels. This will enhance individual and collective resilience, promote sustainability, and foster active social participation, preparing new generations to effectively anticipate, prevent, and confront the threats and challenges of a constantly changing world.

3.3.3 Communications by experts from England

3.3.3.1 DCE initiatives implemented focused on the challenges of climate change

The presentation by Dr. Sara-Jayne Williams focuses on various research projects and research informed initiatives implemented in schools and universities that address the challenges of climate change. Four projects were showcased: VIP-CLEAR, CATAPULT, Reading for the Climate, and Buzzing about Bees

1) The VIP-CLEAR² (Voices in a Pandemic: Children's lockdown experiences applied to recovery) project, funded by the AHRC, explored the impact of COVID-19 on the learning, development, and well-being of children in Bristol, UK. The primary aim was to collaborate with children to authentically capture their experiences and viewpoints during the pandemic, ensuring their voices were included in shaping recovery efforts focused on preschool and primary schools (4-12 years) based in: Creative diary, deep mapping, photo elicitation, Trees of Hope, and Ambition (Webber et al 2022; Williams et al. 2023).

The Challenge was ensuring methodological rigor and consistency across different schools and facilitators. One of the innovative methods used was the "Tree of Hope and Ambition," an arts-based approach that encouraged children

² Voices in a Pandemic: Children's lockdown experiences applied to recovery - and the website is <https://voicesinapandemic.org/>

to reflect on their hopes and needs for the future in relation to COVID-19. Key project aims included:

- Exploring the worldviews and experiences of socially disadvantaged children during the COVID-19 response.
- Drawing actionable insights from children's own perspectives to inform recovery strategies.
- Building resilience and anticipatory skills in preparation for future societal shocks, including pandemics.

The project developed a child-centered, recovery-linked creative diary process, integrating mapping, photography, and artistic exploration (<https://voicesinapandemic.org/>). This creative, child-centred, flexible, inclusive, and holistic approach allowed for deeper engagement

The success of this project was based on working closely with schools, maintaining regular communication, and integrating diverse creative approaches.

2) The CCC-CATAPULT³ project, involving Universities in the UK, Italy, Finland, and Ireland, sought to understand how young people experience the climate crisis in diverse cultural settings and how they can be empowered to become ambassadors for transformation. The challenge of this project was to establish a certain coherence in international projects, as the process including delivering longitudinal parallel co-productive processes considering multiple educational and cultural contexts (Portus et al. 2024). Project methods included:

- Stage 1: Surveys with 1,879 participants aged 15-18, capturing their climate change experiences, beliefs, and actions.
- Stage 2: 21 focus groups with over 100 young people to explore climate values and learning.
- Stage 3: 20 narrative workshops investigating young people's connection to place and their visions for transformative learning.

Key learning outcomes emphasized the importance of strong partnerships, consistency in methodology, adaptive feedback, and integrating diverse educational practices. The success of the project is based on collaborative work with young people, adaptable approaches, and leveraging strengths derived from intercultural perspectives.

³ <https://ccc-catapult.org/>

3) The initiative "Reading for the Climate" aimed to foster climate agency among university students by establishing a climate book club. The project focused on university students (18–30 years old). Twelve undergraduates from various disciplines were recruited, provided with a copy of Neal Shusterman's "Dry," and participated in structured discussions and reflective sessions. The book club emphasized accessibility, informality, and enjoyment, focusing on meaningful engagement rather than formal instruction. Setup highlights included:

- Circular seating, refreshments, and free books to create a welcoming environment.
- Careful book selection to ensure relevance and diversity of interest.
- Discussion led by literature experts using open-ended prompts to spark reflection without directing interpretation.

Challenge: Sustaining engagement through longitudinal research and repeated participation. A focus group, distinct yet connected to the club, encouraged more profound reflections from students who completed the book, facilitated in a relaxed atmosphere with food and guided prompts (Williams et al. 2024).

Key lessons emerged around the value of incentives, thoughtful planning, flexibility, and sustained communication to support active, ongoing engagement. Success: Allowing for empathy and connection, Incentives like books and refreshments, careful planning for a flexible and enjoyable club atmosphere, and open communication.

Buzzing About Bees: Engaging Young Learners

This project engaged primary school children (7–10 years) through storytelling and dance workshops centered on "Bibi the Bee." Activities were designed to be interactive and fun, with group surveys and focus groups used to capture feedback (Portus et al. 2025).

Challenge: Managing large group sizes and responding to diverse teacher needs.

Success stemmed from:

- Incorporating playful, creative activities to make learning accessible.
- Ensuring emotional safety and comfort in large groups.
- Designing subtle, age-appropriate entry points for discussing complex topics.

The suite of projects collectively championed co-production and curriculum-linked research. Approaches ranged from whole-class activities to small group

work, with an emphasis on the "good child" scenario—locating research within supportive, flexible, and inclusive settings. Success factors included:

- Flexible timing, often aligning with the end of school terms to reduce conflicts with assessments.
- Incentives and reciprocal partnerships with advisors and schools.
- Efficient use of resources and clear communication through school brokers.
- Diversity and accessibility throughout the research process.

3.3.3.2 Reflections on DCE with children

Dr. Yildiz's presentation focuses on reflections on DCE. She explains that in UK schools, DCE is part of science and geography subjects. In science, between ages 11 and 14, students explore topics such as the greenhouse effect, the carbon cycle, and the influence of fossil fuels. In geography, between ages 11 and 16, they study global warming and natural hazards, as well as case studies such as the Haiti earthquake and Typhoon Haiyan. Despite this presence in the curriculum, there are notable deficiencies, such as limited practical preparation for local risks, such as floods or forest fires. Furthermore, not all schools have mandatory disaster training, creating inequalities between schools. Another issue is that emergency drills and resources often focus on school staff, leaving students in the background. Finally, teachers lack sufficient training in resilience and emergency response, which diminishes educational effectiveness.

The lack of adequate preparation has obvious consequences. According to recent research, the number of school days lost due to extreme events could increase to twelve days per year by 2050. Furthermore, children face negative impacts on their mental health and well-being, conditions exacerbated by the digital divide, which limits access to the technological tools necessary for disaster preparedness and response.

In this context, ethical dilemmas arise that require a careful approach. Working with children requires rigorous ethical approval and sensitivity to avoid causing anxiety or misinformation. It is essential to promote child participation without generating pressure or emotional overload. When considering transformative proposals, it is essential to foster collaboration with community organizations recognized by schools and families. Furthermore, the use of playful methods such as simulation games, storytelling, and drawing facilitates student learning and active participation in the DCE.

The integration of artificial intelligence into DCE, along with other emerging technologies, opens up promising possibilities by enabling personalized learning, creating interactive simulations, and enhancing educational efficiency. However, it also poses challenges such as privacy issues, the potential for heightened fear among students, and the digital divide that excludes those without access to technology. Furthermore, there is a risk of losing human connection, essential for education and emotional support.

To address these challenges, Dr. Yilliz recommends an ethical approach centered on co-creation. This involves holding co-design workshops with adolescents, implementing tests in informal and safe environments, and establishing ongoing ethical review processes based on feedback from the school community. It is also essential to prioritize the inclusion of vulnerable populations, such as migrants, older adults, and young people.

This requires a framework centered on governance, encompassing policy development and infrastructure strengthening, as well as education that promotes formal learning and volunteering, and technology, including early warnings and the recognition of Indigenous knowledge. Yilliz proposes the KIDA model, centered on stages for transformative education: first, knowledge about risks, past events, and local vulnerabilities; then, generating interest through interactive tools and narratives; then, the desire to act linked to a sense of social responsibility; and finally, action through simulations, campaigns, and community engagement.

Risk-informed education requires promoting experiential learning, fostering co-learning and collaboration among the entire school community, and incorporating values that strengthen social resilience. In this regard, it is crucial to develop educational governance focused on DRR, train and motivate teaching and administrative staff, and prepare schools to face extreme scenarios. Furthermore, reliable communication about invisible and emerging risks must be ensured, both conventional technologies and innovative tools must be used, and the full inclusion of the entire population, including the most vulnerable, must be guaranteed.

3.4 Working group discussion

After the above presentations, participants were divided into groups to have concrete discussions to consider the following questions.

3.4.1 What research, questions, methods, or theories do we need to explore?

The first round of working groups addressed the question: “What research questions, methods, or theories do we need to explore?” The discussion aimed to identify how DCE can be effectively integrated into diverse educational contexts, particularly within the three countries under study. Participants sought to define research priorities, focal areas, and key dimensions for understanding how to teach young people about disasters and citizenship in ways that are practical, sustainable, and culturally relevant—ultimately motivating a shift from knowledge to action. The results of this discussion were summarized in the flipchart shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3: Results reflected in the first working group

What research questions/methods/theories do we need to explore?

RQ

- How to introduce DRR at schools? + sustain it
DCE
- How to bridge the gap between knowledge/awareness and action!
values
- What is a methodology for DRE in 3 countries?
common and localized
- What are the systemic issues in DCE in 3 countries?
- How do we embed DCE in current curricula?

Themes

- Young people's responsibilities/whose responsibility
- Values and cultures
- Risk literacy
- Through informal learning

Methods/theories

- Intergenerational approaches
- Stages
- Co-productive models
- Longitudinal approaches
- Transformative learning and experiential learning
- Radical questioning
- Edge emotion
- Reflective writing

To answer the initial question, five Research Questions (RQs) were posed. These address the significant problems or challenges identified by participants:

1. How to introduce DCE at schools?
2. How to bridge the gap between knowledge (values)/ awareness and Action.

3. What is a (common and localized) methodology for DCE in 3 countries?
4. What are the systemic issues in DCE in 3 countries?
5. How we embed DCE in current curricula?

The core themes identified for effective DCE are:

- Youth responsibility → to what extent they should take an active role.
- Values and cultures → how they influence the way we learn and act.
- Risk literacy → teaching how to understand and manage risks.
- Informal learning → not everything is achieved in the classroom; learning also takes place outside of it.

Regarding the methods and theories suggested for addressing the challenges, they are presented through different approaches:

- Intergenerational → working with different generations together.
- Co-productive → collaborative research and action among stakeholders.
- Longitudinal → following processes over time.
- Transformative and experiential → practical learning that changes attitudes.
- Radical questioning → challenging assumptions.
- Edge emotion → exploring intense emotions as a driver of learning.
- Reflective writing → using written reflection as an educational tool.
- Stages → thinking about the educational process in phases.

3.4.2 What questions can be included in a competency framework?

The second round of working groups, which were reflected in the Flipchart described in Figure 4, focused on the question: "What questions can be included in a 'competency framework'?" Starting from this central question, a set of related questions about life, education, crises, and community preparedness unfolds. Several building blocks can be identified:

1. Existential and Personal Questions

- How do we learn to live?
- How do we want to live and die?
- How do we find comfort in dark times?
- How do we navigate life and death, loss, and uncertainty?
- How do we ensure we are well?
- How do we respond to the unexpected?

These questions address emotional, ethical, and personal resilience competencies.

2. Collective and Community Competencies

- Whose competencies are these?
- How do we create communities of solidarity?
- What unites us or separates us?
- Where do we belong?
- How do we co-learn and build community?

Participants highlight the need to improve social, community, and intergenerational skills.

3. Disaster and Crisis Management

- What types of disasters?
- How do we communicate about a disaster?
- How do we adapt our skills?
- How do we prepare for...?
- Can we turn a crisis into an opportunity?
- How can we track diverse groups?

The need to acquire risk preparedness, response, and recovery skills is noted.

4. Intergenerational Education and Preparedness

Includes ideas on:

- Educational agents
- Intergenerational relationships
- Preparation, recovery, and post-recovery
- What do we need to teach for the next hazard?

The importance of preventive education and intergenerational learning transmission is highlighted.

5. Future Vision and Action

- Who is responsible?
- How do we want to live together in the future?
- How can we organize ourselves more flexibly, legally, and effectively to achieve goals?

- Creating desire and interest for change.

This block focuses on competencies of vision, leadership, and transformative action.

Figure 4: Results reflected in the second working group

The participants propose that a competency framework should not only focus on technical skills, but also on more profound questions about how to live, cope with uncertainty, take care of ourselves, build community, and transform crises into opportunities. Furthermore, it emphasizes the role of education, intergenerational relationships, and disaster preparedness as key elements.

3.4.3 What expertise will we draw into DCE research?

The central question of the third round of working groups, "What expertise will we draw into DCE research?", raises the need to identify and articulate the different types of knowledge that should be integrated into research on DCE. Six key points emerge from this question, which were reflected in the Flipchart described in Figure 5.

Figure 5: Results reflected in the third working group

1. Connecting practice and research

A fundamental first axis is the bridge between practitioners and academic research. This involves not only the participation of civil protection experts, local services, schools, and NGOs, but also the active involvement of politicians and policymakers, who are responsible for transforming knowledge into public policy. For this bridge to be viable, practical communication skills are necessary to convey findings clearly and facilitate intersectoral collaboration.

2. Experiential Knowledge and Impacted Voices

Practical experience comes not only from organized professionals, but also from people directly affected by disasters or in vulnerable situations (immigrants, older adults, communities with special needs). The importance of integrating these voices is emphasized, as they are often excluded from formal research but provide deeply valuable, situated knowledge for understanding the real consequences of these phenomena.

3. Theoretical and Comparative Dimension

Research in DCE relies on theoretical and comparative analysis, which allows for learning from diverse contexts. Examples mentioned include studies on Japan, European discourse, and the use of "soft power" in risk management and climate narratives. However, the existence of a gap in current research is also

acknowledged, highlighting the need to broaden perspectives, for example, through new studies such as those conducted in collaboration with schools and civil protection in Valencia.

4. Cultural, Traditional, and Local Knowledge

Another pillar is the valorization of local and cultural knowledge, including:

- Indigenous knowledge linked to the environment.
- Experiences transmitted through social and historical memory.
- Urban planning practices (urban planning knowledge).
- Forms of community resilience built over time.

It is recognized that this type of knowledge can offer adaptive and sustainable responses, provided it is integrated into networks that allow for exchange and updating through scientific research.

5. Necessary Voices and Conversations

It is noted that many voices have historically been ignored. Building a solid field of research in climate and disaster education must open a space for conversations between:

- National systems,
- theories,
- academic disciplines,
- institutions,
- and individuals.

This participatory approach not only enriches research but also legitimizes practices by recognizing the diversity of perspectives.

6. Educational and Pedagogical Dimension

Finally, education is a key area for articulating all this knowledge. The following competencies stand out as necessary:

- Ethics and citizenship, including reflection on artificial intelligence and its impact.
- Critical thinking and the ability to address controversial issues.
- Media literacy is essential for managing information overload and fake news in crisis contexts.

Connections between teachers and students, who not only act as recipients of knowledge but also as active agents in building social resilience.

3.5 Summary of working group discussion

The involvement of various stakeholders in DCE, not only as passive recipients of information but also as active agents in building social resilience, poses significant challenges and opportunities in the educational and social spheres. This participatory perspective fosters greater legitimacy in practices and enables the integration of diverse perspectives and experiences, thereby enriching both research and decision-making.

From an educational perspective, the need to incorporate skills such as ethics, citizenship, critical thinking, and media literacy becomes particularly relevant. In a context where information about a disaster is abundant and often contradictory or inaccurate, these skills enable individuals not only to manage data better but also to critically question and reflect on the impact of technologies, such as artificial intelligence, on society.

Furthermore, recognizing the plurality of theories, academic disciplines, institutions, and individuals with diverse approaches to disaster risk reduction contributes to strengthening social resilience in the face of crises or global challenges. Education, therefore, is a privileged space for articulating knowledge and fostering active citizen participation in solving complex problems. Promoting active participation and the development of critical and ethical competencies in disaster risk management is crucial for advancing toward a more resilient society, one that can adapt and respond effectively to the challenges posed by climate change.

4. Conclusion

The analysis conducted throughout the symposium, based on the contributions of participants through their communications and participation in the discussion groups, highlights the fundamental importance of DCE as a driving force for building a resilient society in the face of the challenges arising from climate change and disaster risk management. As observed in the three documents describing the legal context and key practices of DCE, while Germany, Spain, and England have developed regulatory frameworks and policies that recognize this role, the reality shows that the effective integration of these contents and competencies into educational systems is still a process underway, subject to

significant inequalities depending on the national and regional context. For example, in Spain, recent efforts to introduce DCE as a mandatory part of the school curriculum represent a significant advance; however, their success will depend on teacher training, the provision of resources, and the ongoing evaluation of results, all of which still present challenges.

In this sense, formal and non-formal education must go beyond the mere transmission of technical knowledge, embracing a holistic and collaborative approach that actively involves communities, public agencies, the private sector, and civil society. Practical experience shows that citizen participation and the inclusion of diverse perspectives, including those of traditionally marginalized or vulnerable groups, enrich decision-making and foster a stronger culture of prevention. Thus, community projects, school emergency drills, and platforms for intergenerational dialogue emerge as excellent examples of how education can become a space for genuine social transformation.

However, technical training in disaster prevention, management, and response must be complemented by the development of cross-cutting skills. The emotional management of emergency teams, the psychological resilience of learners and educators, and the strengthening of critical thinking and media literacy are essential aspects. In a world of information overabundance and misinformation, people must learn to discern reliable sources, question narratives, and understand the scope and limitations of disruptive technologies such as artificial intelligence. Educational programs that incorporate debates on ethics, digital citizenship, and the critical analysis of information are becoming increasingly necessary to prepare citizens for complex and unforeseen crises.

In the medium and long term, educational research and innovation in this area must be at the heart of future strategies. The integration of active methodologies, such as problem-based learning, collaborative projects, and gamification, facilitates the acquisition of key skills and motivates individuals to actively participate in risk management and in the adaptation to climate change. Likewise, international cooperation and the exchange of best practices between countries and researchers involved in DCE can help overcome structural and cultural barriers, thereby accelerating the transition toward more flexible and inclusive education systems that are better prepared for the global challenges posed by climate change and its consequences.

Based on the results of this symposium, we can conclude that building a critical, supportive, and resilient citizenry requires understanding DCE as a continuous, cross-cutting, and deeply contextualized process. Only from an integrative perspective, which articulates scientific knowledge, ethical values, and active participation, will it be possible to move toward societies capable of anticipating, adapting, and responding in innovative and effective ways to the environmental risks and challenges caused by present and future climate change.

Key Messages/ Summary

1. **Education is a key aspect** of protecting the environment and building a resilient society.
2. **Education for disaster risk reduction and education for climate change adaptation are closely linked.** Combining both approaches as DCE can open up new potential.
3. DCE encompasses **lifelong learning for all people** and takes particular account of vulnerable individuals. To this end, those affected should be more closely involved in research and the development of educational approaches.
4. **There is a need for research** in the field of DCE. This requires the development of clearly defined research questions, focus areas and theoretical frameworks to serve as guidelines.
5. **Context-specific approaches** should take into account cultural and national differences in education systems and conditions. Differences and the potential of communities should be taken into account.

References

Bundesamt für Bevölkerungsschutz und Katastrophenhilfe (BBK). (n.d.). *Was sind die Ziele des Bundesweiten Warntags?*

https://www.bbk.bund.de/DE/Warnung-Vorsorge/Bundesweiter-Warntag/Ziele-bundesweiter-Warntag/ziele-bundesweiter-warntag_node.html

Bundesamt für Bevölkerungsschutz und Katastrophenhilfe (BBK). (2020). *Gesetz über den Zivilschutz und die Katastrophenhilfe des Bundes (Zivilschutz- und Katastrophenhilfegesetz - ZSKG).*

https://www.bbk.bund.de/SharedDocs/Downloads/DE/Rechtsgrundlagen/zskg.pdf?__blob=publicationFile&v=8

Bundesministerium für Bildung und Forschung (BMBF). (n.d.). *BNEhoch3: Kostenlose BNE-Weiterbildung für Multiplikatorinnen und Multiplikatoren.*

<https://www.bne-portal.de/bne/de/infothek/bnehoch3.html>

Chadderton, C. (2015). Civil defence pedagogies and narratives of democracy: disaster education in Germany. *International Journal of Lifelong Education*, 34(5), 589–606. <https://doi.org/10.1080/02601370.2015.1073186>

Cook, J., D. Nuccitelli, S.A. Green, M. Richardson, B. Winkler, R. Painting, R. Way, P. Jacobs, & A. Skuce (2013). Quantifying the consensus on anthropogenic global warming in the scientific literature. *Environmental Research Letters*, 8, 024024. <https://doi.org/10.1088/1748-9326/8/2/024024>.

Cook, J., Oreskes, N., Doran, P.T., Anderegg, W.R.L., Verheggen, B., Mailbach, E.W., Carlton, J.S., Lewandowsky, S., Skuce, A.G., Green, S.A., Nuccitelli, D., Jacobs, P., Richardson, M., Winkler, B., Painting, R., Rice, K. (2016). Consensus on consensus: A synthesis of consensus estimates on human-caused global warming. *Environmental Research Letters*, 11, 048002. <https://doi.org/10.1088/1748-9326/11/4/048002>.

Department for Education, United Kingdom (DfE). (2024). *Health and safety: Advice on legal duties and powers For local authorities, school leaders, school staff and governing bodies.* Department for Education.

Department for Education, United Kingdom (DfE). (2023). *Sustainability and climate change: A strategy for the education and children's services systems.* GOV.UK. <https://www.gov.uk/government/publications/sustainability-and-climate-change-strategy/sustainability-and-climate-change-a-strategy-for-the-education-and-childrens-services-systems>

Doran, P., and M.K. Zimmerman (2009). Examining the Scientific Consensus on Climate Change. *Eos*, 90(3), 22–23. <https://doi.org/10.1029/2009EO030002>

Eschenbacher, S. (2023). Saving lives: an unsustainable profession –a study of transformative learning at work, *Studies in Continuing Education*, 46(2), 266–281. <https://doi.org/10.1080/0158037X.2023.2222068>

Eschenbacher, S., & Marsick, V. J. (2024) Getting it off your soul: transformative conversations for processing traumatic experiences. *Reflective Practice*, 25(6), 813–825. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14623943.2024.2406967>

European Environment Agency (EEA) (2024). *European climate risk assessment (EEA Report No 1/2024)*. <https://www.eea.europa.eu/publications/european-climate-risk-assessment>

Gavari-Starkie, E., Pastrana-Huguet, J., Navarro-González, I., & Espinosa-Gutiérrez, P.-T. (2021). The Inclusion of Resilience as an Element of the Sustainable Dimension in the LOMLOE Curriculum in a European Framework. *Sustainability*, 13(24), 13714. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su132413714>

Geicht, S. K. (2022). Langsam besser vorbereitet? Neue Eindrücke aus der Evaluation der Informationskampagne Selbstschutz. *Bevölkerungsschutz*(3), 30–36.

Dirección General de Protección Civil y Emergencias (2021). Plan Estatal General de Emergencias de Protección Civil. PLEGEM. https://www.interior.gob.es/opencms/pdf/archivos-y-documentacion/documentacion-y-publicaciones/publicaciones-descargables/proteccion-civil/PLEGEM_126210029_web.pdf

Gobierno de España (2021). *Ley 7/2021, de 20 de mayo, de cambio climático y transición energética*. https://www.boe.es/diario_boe/txt.php?id=BOE-A-2021-8447

Gobierno de España. (2015). *Ley 17/2015, de 9 de julio, del Sistema Nacional de Protección Civil*. <https://www.boe.es/buscar/act.php?id=BOE-A-2015-7730>

Gobierno de España (2020). *Ley Orgánica 3/2020, de 29 de diciembre, por la que se modifica la Ley Orgánica 2/2006, de 3 de mayo, de Educación (LOMLOE)*. <https://www.boe.es/buscar/doc.php?id=BOE-A-2020-17264>

Gobierno de España. (2023). *Real Decreto 524/2023, de 20 de junio, por el que se aprueba la Norma Básica de Protección Civil*. <https://www.boe.es/buscar/act.php?id=BOE-A-2023-14679>

Gobierno de España. (2013). *Real Decreto 906/2013, de 22 de noviembre, por el que se establece el título de Técnico Superior en Coordinación de Emergencias y Protección Civil y se fijan sus enseñanzas mínimas.* https://www.boe.es/diario_boe/txt.php?id=BOE-A-2013-13163

Gobierno de España. (2013). *Real Decreto 907/2013, de 22 de noviembre, por el que se establece el título de Técnico en Emergencias y Protección Civil y se fijan sus enseñanzas mínimas.* https://www.boe.es/diario_boe/txt.php?id=BOE-A-2013-13164

Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC). (2018). *Global warming of 1.5 °C: An IPCC special report on the impacts of global warming of 1.5 °C above pre-industrial levels and related global greenhouse gas emission pathways, in the context of strengthening the global response to the threat of climate change, sustainable development, and efforts to eradicate poverty.* <https://www.ipcc.ch/sr15/>

Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC). (2023). *Sixth Assessment Report (AR6).* <https://www.ipcc.ch/assessment-report/ar6/>

Kitagawa, K. (2021). Conceptualising 'Disaster Education'. *Education Sciences, 11*(5), 233. <https://doi.org/10.3390/educsci11050233>

Kitagawa, K. (2023). Learning and Teaching of Climate Change, Sustainability and Disaster Risk Reduction in Teacher Education in England and Japan. *Journal of Teacher Education for Sustainability, 25*(2), 5–20. <https://doi.org/10.2478/jtes-2023-0013>

Kitagawa, K., Preston, J., & Chadderton, C. (2016). Preparing for disaster: a comparative analysis of education for critical infrastructure collapse. *Journal of Risk Research, 20*(11), 1450–1465. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13669877.2016.1178661>

Kultusministerkonferenz (KMK). (2024). *Empfehlung der Kultusministerkonferenz zur Bildung für nachhaltige Entwicklung in der Schule: (Beschluss der Kultusministerkonferenz vom 13.06.2024).* https://www.kmk.org/fileadmin/veroeffentlichungen_beschluesse/2024/2024_06_13-BNE-Empfehlung.pdf

Lacher, S. (2025). Exploring Disaster Preparedness: A Scoping Review of Adult and Continuing Education Approaches in International Civil Protection Research. *Journal of Risk Research, 1*–17. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1080/13669877.2024.2447252>

Lacher, S., & Rohs, M. (2023). Civil protection through adult and continuing education in Germany. A scoping review of an emerging research field. *International Journal of Lifelong Education*, 42(6), 532-549. <https://doi.org/10.1080/02601370.2023.2263651>

National Aeronautics and Space Administration (NASA). (2024). *Effects of climate change* [Web page]. NASA Science. <https://science.nasa.gov/climate-change/effects/>

National Flood Forum. (2020). *Who We Are*. National Flood Forum. <https://nationalfloodforum.org.uk/how-we-help/who-we-are/>

National Platform on Education for Sustainable Development. (2017). *National Action Plan on Education for Sustainable Development: The German contribution to the UNESCO Global Action Programme*. https://www.bne-portal.de/bne/shareddocs/downloads/files/bmbf_nap_bne_en_screen_2.pdf?_blob=publicationFile&v=5

Oreskes, N. (2004). The Scientific Consensus on Climate Change. *Science*, 306, 1686. <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.1103618>.

Oreskes, N. (2018). The scientific consensus on climate change: How do we know we're not wrong? *Climate Modelling*, pp. 31-64. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-65058-6_2.

Olcina, J., & Morote, Álvaro-F. (2025). Enseñar a convivir con el riesgo. Importancia del Marco de Sendai para la Reducción del Riesgo de Desastres (2015-2030). *Revista Ciència Geográfica*, 29(1). <https://doi.org/10.18817/26755122.29.1.2025.4166>

Pastrana Huguet, J. (2024). *Estudio comparativo entre España y Japón sobre la reducción del riesgo de desastres. Aportaciones para la promoción de la cultura preventiva y la creación de comunidades resilientes*. Tesis doctoral, Universidad Nacional de Educación a Distancia (España)

Portus, R., Williams, S. J., Mansikka-aho, A., Reilly, K., Aarnio-Linnanvuori, E., De Vito, L., Dillon, B., Fahy, F., Gnecco, I., Palla, A., Sposito, S. & McEwen, L. (2024). Reflections on co-productive research in a youth-focused climate education project. *Geographical Research*, 63(1), 118-133. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1745-5871.12642>

Portus, R., Williams, S. J., Peklanska, E., Portus, R., & Walmsley, T. (2025). Buzzing about bees: exploring action-based storytelling as a tool for children's environmental engagement and agency. *Environmental Education Research*, 31(5), 1048-1068. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13504622.2025.2478430>

Preston, J. (Ed.). (2012). *Disaster Education: 'Race', Equity and Pedagogy*. Springer.

Rohs, M., & Lacher, S. (Eds.). (2025). *Ratgeber für Notfälle. Eine Analyse des Nutzens aus Perspektive des Bevölkerungsschutzes* (Vol. 16). RPTU. <https://nbn-resolving.org/urn:nbn:de:hbz:386-kluedo-92067>.

Rohs, M., Lacher, S., & Großmann, J. (Eds.). (2025). *Notfall- und Katastrophenvorsorge in Deutschland. Ergebnisse einer repräsentativen Bevölkerungsbefragung* (Vol. 17). RPTU. <https://nbn-resolving.org/urn:nbn:de:hbz:386-kluedo-92087>.

Sharpe, J., & Kelman, I. (2011). Improving the disaster-related component of secondary school geography education in England. *International Research in Geographical and Environmental Education*, 20(4), 327–343. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10382046.2011.619810>

Shaw, R., Shiwaku, K., & Takeuchi, Y. (Eds.). (2011). *Disaster education*. Emerald Group Publishing.

Shiwaku, K., Sakurai, A., & Shaw, R. (2016). *Disaster resilience of education systems*. Springer

Lacher, S., & Rohs, M. (2024). Erwachsenenbildung als Beitrag zu einer Katastrophenvorsorge: Eine empirische Untersuchung zu Informations- und Lernangeboten für den Hochwasserschutz. In M. Ebner von Eschenbach, B. Käßlinger, M. Kondratjuk, K. Kraus, M. Rohs, B. Schmidt-Hertha, K. J. Rott, & V. Thalhammer (Eds.), *Erwachsenenbildung und Nachhaltigkeit: Sondierungen und Forschung zwischen Anspruch und Wirklichkeit* (pp.129–141). Verlag Barbara Budrich.

Lynas, M., Houlton, B. Z., & Perry, S. (2021). Greater than 99% consensus on human caused climate change in the peer-reviewed scientific literature. *Environmental Research Letters*, 16(11), 114005. <https://doi.org/10.1088/1748-9326/ac2966>

Navarro-González, I., Zhou, C., & Svabo, C. (2024). *Importance and mastery of soft skills in teacher education students*[Unpublished manuscript]

The Federal Government. (2022). *German Strategy for Strengthening Resilience to Disasters: Implementing the Sendai Framework for Disaster Risk Reduction (2015–2030) – Germany's contribution 2022–2030*. Summary. Federal Ministry of the Interior and Community (BMI). <https://www.bbk.bund.de/SharedDocs/Downloads/DE/Mediathek/Publikation>

[en/Sendai-Katrima/deutsche-strategie-resilienz-kurz-eng_download.pdf?__blob=publicationFile&v=4](#)

United Kingdom Government. (2015). *Equality Act 2010: Guidance*. GOV.UK. <https://www.gov.uk/guidance/equality-act-2010-guidance>

United Kingdom Government. (2019). *Climate change*. GOV.UK. <https://www.gov.uk/guidance/climate-change>

United Kingdom Government. (2022). *Health and safety: Responsibilities and duties for schools*. GOV.UK. <https://www.gov.uk/government/publications/health-and-safety-advice-for-schools/responsibilities-and-duties-for-schools>

United Kingdom Government. (2024a). *Prepare for flooding* [Flooding]. GOV.UK. <https://www.gov.uk/prepare-for-flooding>

United Kingdom Government. (2024b). *Understanding climate adaptation and the third National Adaptation Programme (NAP3)*. GOV.UK. <https://www.gov.uk/government/publications/third-national-adaptation-programme-nap3/understanding-climate-adaptation-and-the-third-national-adaptation-programme-nap3>

United Nations Office for Disaster Risk Reduction (UNDRR), (2005). *Hyogo Framework for Action 2005-2015: Building the resilience of nations and communities to disasters*.

United Nations Office for Disaster Risk Reduction (UNDRR), (2015). *Sendai Framework for Disaster Risk Reduction 2015-2030*.

Webber, A. D., Jones, V., McEwen, L., Deave, T., Gorell Barnes, L., Williams, S., Hobbs, L., Fogg-Rogers, L. & Gopinath, D. (2024). Voices in a pandemic: using deep mapping to explore children's sense of place during the COVID-19 pandemic in UK. *Children's Geographies*, 22(4), 565-580. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14733285.2024.2315153>

Williams, S., McEwen, L. J., Gorell Barnes, L., Deave, T., Webber, A., Jones, V., Fogg-Rogers, L., Gopinath, D. & Hobbs, L. (2023). The Tree (s) of Hope and Ambition: An arts-based social science informed, participatory research method to explore children's future hopes, ambitions and support in relation to COVID-19. *Children & Society*, 37(5), 1356-1375. <https://doi.org/10.1111/chso.12767>

Williams, S. J., Portus, R., Roberston, S., & Alston, A. (2025). Reading slowly together: climate literature book clubs and their potential for engaging young

people with climate crisis. *Environmental Education Research*, 31(11), 2177–2195.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/13504622.2024.2397593>

Citation

Pastrana Huguet, J. et al. (2026). *Disaster and climate education (DCE). Reflections from the 2025 European symposium of the Disaster and Climate Education Network*.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19727206>

Further information on the Disaster and Climate Education Network

<https://sowi.rptu.de/dcen>